

CHURCH LEADERS OF CAMPUS-BASED NEIGHBOURHOOD BAPTIST CHURCHES AND THEIR PERCEPTION OF YOUTH CULTURE

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Abstract: *Youth are special in their approach to almost everything. Hence, the importance of understudying young people in order to help them sail through the youthful stage without 'hitting icebergs that will capsize their boat' cannot be overemphasized. Knowing fully well that church leaders relate with these teeming youth on regular basis, this study investigated the perception of church leaders on youth culture, with a particular interest in campus-based neighbourhood Baptist churches. A descriptive survey research design was used; the population of the study were leaders of churches that are near higher institution campuses within Ekiti Baptist Conference. One hundred (100) leaders were sampled from nine (9) churches close to educational institutions, but seventy (70) church leaders responded to the questionnaire. The instrument used for data gathering was a validated researcher-designed questionnaire with Cronbach's Alpha correlation co-efficient value 'r' of 0.804. Analysis of the data was done using descriptive analysis of percentages and the percentages were ranked. Wearing of dreadlocks ranked highest as the predominant culture in the perception of church leaders, with a mean score of 1.25. On the other hand, the use of slang ranked lowest with a mean score of 0.78. Considering the importance of youth culture to young people, this study recommends that church leaders should be more deliberate to understand youth cultures that are peculiar to their environment. Youth discipleship should also be given priority in order to shape youth properly for effective imparts among their peers.*

Key Words: Church leaders, Youth, Young people, Youth culture, campus-based, neighbourhood, Baptist churches, perception.

Introduction

Defining who exactly is a youth is an arduous task. This is because more often than not, describing the youth category “may be based on one's social circumstances rather than chronological age or cultural position” (Bucholtz, 2002, p. 526). Despite this difficulty, though, several societies have descriptions of youth based on their peculiarity. The United Nations, on her part, holds it that the age group for the youth is 15 and 24 years without prejudice to the definitions of the member states of the United Nations (“What do You Mean by Youth,” 2018). Africa Charter, however, considers youth in Africa to be people between the ages 15-35 years (African Youth Charter, 2006). It has become glaring to the general populace that the population of young people keeps soaring higher on daily basis. In some countries, birth control has been

firmly established, while in some others, it is still forthcoming. This, therefore, implies that the population of young people will keep rising by the day. Young people contribute immensely to the world population. According to the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of United Nations, sixteen percent of the world population are young people whose ages range between 15-24 years. This percentage estimated young people's population to 1.2 billion with over 200 million from Sub-Saharan Africa (United Nations, 2019). Nigeria has been adjudged as the country with the largest concentration of young people in the world (United Nations, n.d.). This places a huge task on the shoulders of the Nigerian church.

The expectation is that the church in Nigeria will reach out to this teeming population of

young people and connect them with Jesus Christ, the Lord of the Church. The Baptist Denomination in Nigeria, with the Nigerian Baptist Convention (NBC) as the largest, is one of the denominations that have a ministry to youth. One of the ways she reaches out to the young people in the country is the involvement of campus-based neighbourhood churches in youth ministry. The church is expected to help her youth cultivate a good “attitude towards the church” (Ji & Tameifuna, 2011, p. 307) so as to ensure that when they grow older and become adults, they remain within her and lead other youth to do the same. It will be practically difficult for the church to achieve this goal when her leaders do not understand youth and their culture.

Defining culture is a herculean task. However, some scholars express culture as the uniqueness of a people, which determines their identity, how they think, feel and react, way of life, and behavioural attitudes (Eriksen, 2004; Lebron, 2013; and Eze, 2014). This description shows that in general terms, understanding the culture of a people group leads to an understanding of the people group because “culture affects how people behave” (Adeyemi, 2020, p. 7) and it makes glaring who they are. Hence, the culture of a people determines how they will behave and what they will hold as tenets. The culture of a people group instructs and forms them, even when they may be oblivious of the formative power of their culture.

Borgman (1994) posits that a person does not just crash into his cultural inclination and identity but learns his culture. Such learning can take place in various forms, depending on the type of culture that is to be learnt. The cultural identities that determine a person's belief system and behaviours are learned in a specific cultural milieu. This helps in the formulation of what individuals stand or do not stand for, as well as what they represent. Such cultural identities are transferred from one generation to another.

On his part, Mueller (2006) noted that culture can also be described as “what we believe, what we do, and how we live our lives from day to day. It binds us to those who think, and live in a similar manner” (p. 112). As simple as this description seems, it affirms that a closer examination of what people do daily reveals their culture. Mueller points out six characteristics of

culture, which makes it easy to study and identify. According to him, these characteristics begin with the understanding that God created culture. The second character of culture is its universality, which makes it cut across continents. Next, culture is shared as a system of living for those who live in a particular place. The other characteristics are noted as follows: it can be learned, it is an integrated whole, and it is not static.

Just as Mueller, Eze also believes that culture cannot be restricted to an exact locality because it is delocalized. Culture, according to him, is a phenomenon that cuts across various localities, determining the way of life of people in specific places (Eze, 2014, p. 3). The culture of a people group determines their perception and mode of interaction with other people. Eze's position shows that the culture of a people group may not be limited to them alone. Cultural positions are generally observed among various people groups, even if their cultural dispositions differ from one another.

Based on the works of G. Stanley Hall in the early 1900s, the origin of youth culture was traced to the United States of America at about the 1920s (Moore, 2015). Brake (as cited by Moore, 2007), points out that the term 'youth culture' was first used by the sociologist Talcott Parsons in 1942 (p. 814) in describing the attitudes of young folks. Stanley Hall pointed out that American youth were faced with the enticement of the immoral habits of the cities that accommodated the industries of America at the time. These young people, as indicated by Moore were denied the rites of passage that indicate their movement into adulthood (Moore, 2015). As a response, Hall suggested that schooling years should be extended to allow adolescents to spend more time exploring their adolescent stage while delaying their entry into adult society. The extension in schooling years, therefore, led to an age-specific culture among the students, which was formulated through extracurricular activities and clubs. This culture eventually expanded greatly among adolescents, and it gradually spread to other nations of the world.

Feixa and Nofre (2012), in describing youth culture, note that:

In a wide sense, 'youth cultures' refer to the way in which young people's social experiences are

expressed collectively through the construction of differentiating lifestyles, mainly in their leisure time, or in interstitial spaces in the institutional life. In a more restricted sense, the term defines the emergence of 'youth micro-societies,' with significant degrees of independence from the 'adult institutions,' that provide specific space and time (p. 4).

A look at the description of Feixa and Nofre (2012) stated above shows that youth culture is simply the way young people express themselves through their lifestyles. This expression is done as subcultures that are peculiar to different localities.

Statement of the Problem

From time to time, there are reports of conflicts between the church and young people in several quarters, owing to the influence of youth culture among the youth in these churches. As a result of these incessant conflicts, the relationship of young people and the leaders of the church which ought to be a plus has brought setbacks to youth ministry. While the Nigerian Baptist Convention (NBC) reaches out to young people, a lack of the right perception of youth culture poses a great threat to effectiveness in the ministry to these young people. Therefore, this study investigates the perception of church leaders of campus-based neighbourhood churches to check if the leaders are aware of what goes on among the young people around them. The purpose of this study is to investigate the views of Nigerian Baptist church leaders of campus-based neighbourhood churches on youth culture. Hence, the specific objectives of the study were to: identify predominant youth cultures in campus-based neighbourhood churches and find out the perception of church leaders of campus-based neighbourhood churches on youth culture.

Research Questions

1. What are the youth cultures that are predominant in campus-based neighbourhood churches?
2. What are the perceptions of church leaders of campus-based neighbourhood churches on youth culture?

Methodology

The research design used was descriptive research. The population of the study for this research were pastors, deacons, leaders of MMU, leaders of WMU, youth of churches, and some other leaders of campus-based Baptist churches in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Nine campus-based Baptist churches were selected for this study. The selected churches were First Baptist and New Heritage Baptist Churches, Oye-Ekiti, which are close to the Federal University, Oye-Ekiti; Goshenland Baptist and Light House Baptist Churches, Iworoko-Ekiti, which are close to Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti; Messiah Baptist and Shalom Baptist Churches, Ado-Ekiti, which are close to the main and satellite campuses of the Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti; First Baptist Church Ikere, which is close to the College of Education, Ikere-Ekiti; and First Baptist Church, Ilawe-Ekiti, which is close to Crown Polytechnics, Odo. In each church, the questionnaires were administered to the leaders in the church, with consideration for the population of the number of people that make up the Church Council. Seventy (70) respondents were randomly selected from the nine churches.

The instrument used for data collection was a reliable researcher-designed questionnaire, named 'Church Leaders and Youth Culture.' It was duly validated through a pilot study and subjected to Cronbach's Alpha analysis to arrive at the correlation co-efficient value which was positive with 'r' equal to 0.807. The correlation adjudged the instrument reliable. The responses were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). A descriptive analysis of percentages was used and some of the percentages were also ranked.

Data collection involved the distribution of one hundred (100) copies of the questionnaire; personally taken to each of the churches, after due permission of the church pastors had been obtained. The author also provided further verbal instructions to the church leaders. Seventy copies of the questionnaire were later retrieved and collated from the nine churches. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Church Leaders by sex, age range, designation, and length of service as a leader (N=70)

Demography		F	%	N		
Sex	M	39	55.7	67	0.42	0.497
	F	28	40.0			
Agerange	< 20	4	5.7	70	2.59	1.460
	20-29	14	20.0			
	30-39	20	28.6			
	40-49	9	12.9			
	50-59	15	21.4			
	60-69	8	11.4			
Designation	CP	6	8.6	70	3.99	2.170
	AP	4	5.7			
	DCN	9	12.9			
	CS	8	11.4			
	MMU	13	18.6			
	WMU	12	17.1			
	Youth	5	7.1			
	Others	13	18.6			
Length of service as a leader (years)	< 5	34	48.6	66	0.79	0.886
	6-10	12	17.1			
	> 10	20	28.6			

Source: Field Survey, January 2020

Key: CP-Church Pastor; AP- Associate Pastor; DCN- Deacon; CS- Church Secretary; MMU- Men's Missionary Union Executive Members; WMU- Women's Missionary Union Executive Members

Table 1 reveals that the majority- 39 (55.7 percent) of the respondents were males. 28 of the respondents are females, which represents 40 percent of the respondents. Also, the leaders whose ages fall within the range of 30-39 have the highest percentage of 28.6 percent with a frequency of 20. Respondents who have an age range of less than 20 are the least, with 5.7 percent of the respondents. Next in Table 1 is the designation of the respondents. The executive members of the MMU ranked highest with 18.6 percent of the respondents. This was closely followed by the

WMU, with 17.1 percent of the respondents. The last demographic characteristic in Table 1 is the length of service of the church leaders. It could be observed from the table that church leaders whose service ranged between 6-10 years ranked lowest, representing 17.1 percent of the respondents, while 48.6 percent of the respondents who ranked highest with 34 respondents were leaders who have only been serving for less than five years. Hence, this research should be of great significance for the 'fresh' leaders before they become fixed in their ways.

Results and Findings

Research Question One: What are the predominant youth cultures in campus-based neighbourhood churches?

Table 2: Church Leaders' Response on Predominant Youth Cultures in Campus-based Neighbourhood Churches

	Statements	SA		A		D		SD		N			RANK
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%				
1.	Colour of Hair	29	41.4	29	41.4	8	11.4	4	5.7	70	0.81	0.856	8 th
2.	Socks on slippers	23	32.9	26	37.1	15	21.4	5	7.1	69	1.03	0.923	3 rd
3.	Blazers without tucking in the shirt.	12	17.1	38	54.3	15	21.4	4	5.7	69	1.16	0.779	2 nd
4.	Dreadlock	14	20.0	28	40.0	16	22.9	7	10.0	65	1.25	0.919	1 st
5.	Use of slangs	12	17.1	38	54.3	15	21.4	4	5.7	69	0.78	0.783	9 th
6.	Shaping the beard in different styles	25	35.7	30	42.9	13	18.6	1	1.4	69	0.86	0.772	6 th
7.	Wearing Trousers not reaching the ankle.	20	28.6	34	48.6	13	18.6	3	4.3	70	0.99	0.807	4 th
8.	Various dancing styles	25	35.7	32	45.7	11	15.7	2	2.9	70	0.86	0.785	6 th
9.	Use of heavy make-ups (or make-over).	19	27.1	33	47.1	13	18.6	2	2.9	68	0.97	0.778	5 th

Source: Field Survey, January 2020

Table 2 above shows the responses of church leaders based on the identification of some predominant youth culture markers in campus-based neighbourhood churches. Responding to whether some youth in the area wear socks on slippers or not, Table 2 reveals that thirty-seven point one (37.1) percent and thirty two point nine (32.9) percent – making a total of 70 percent of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively to the statement. However, twenty-one point four (21.4) percent and seven point one (7.1) percent of the respondents, both disagreed and strongly disagreed with this statement. Table 2 further reveals that a total of seventy-one point four

(71.4) percent of the respondents both strongly agreed and agreed with the statement that some youth wear blazers without tucking in their inner shirts; while a total of twenty-seven point one (27.1) percent of the respondents both disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. In summary, church leaders strongly agreed and agreed that the predominant youth culture around them were dreadlocks, wearing blazers without tucking in the shirt, and wearing socks with slippers in public. **Research Question Two:** What are the perceptions of church leaders of campus-based neighbourhood churches on youth culture?

Table 3: Church Leaders' Perception of Youth Culture

	Statement	NT		ST		OT		T		AT		N		σ	RANK
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%				
1.	Lifestyle vs. salvation.	7	10.0	8	11.4	10	14.3	32	45.7	10	14.3	67	2.45	1.197	5 th
2.	Double lives.	3	4.3	5	7.1	10	14.3	35	50.0	15	21.4	68	2.79	1.016	1 st
3.	No slangs	5	7.1	7	10.0	9	12.9	31	44.3	16	22.9	68	2.68	1.165	2 nd
4.	Slangs vs. Discipline	7	10.0	8	11.4	4	5.7	27	38.6	18	25.7	64	2.64	1.314	3 rd
5.	Understanding youth peculiarities	29	41.4	13	18.6	8	11.4	14	20.0	3	4.3	67	1.24	1.327	9 th
6.	No to choreography	24	34.3	18	25.7	8	11.4	13	18.6	5	7.1	68	1.37	1.337	8 th
7.	Sharp rebuke	15	21.4	10	14.3	16	22.9	17	24.3	9	12.9	67	1.93	1.363	6 th
8.	Less freedom to curb excesses.	6	8.6	7	10.0	15	21.4	23	32.9	17	24.3	68	2.56	1.226	4 th
9.	Don't involve youth in leadership	22	31.4	16	22.9	11	15.7	13	18.6	6	8.6	68	1.49	1.355	7 th

Source: Field Survey, January 2020

Tables 3 above presents the responses of the church leaders to the second research question, which focuses on the perceptions of church leaders on youth culture. As shown in Table 3, church leaders are of the strong opinion that youth live double lives when under the influence of youth culture. This view ranked first with a total of seventy-one point four (71.4) percent of the respondents holding the view that it is both true and always true that youth live double standard lives, especially through the way they dress. This is quite higher than the total of twenty-five point seven (25.7) percent of the respondents who think that the statement is not true, seldom true, and often true. The view of the church leaders on the usage of slang among youth during their communication with one another ranked second. Forty-four point three (44.3) percent and twenty-two point nine (22.9) of the respondents are of the view that a saved youth would not use slang when communicating with others. These give a total of sixty-seven point two (67.2) percent. In summary, ranking highest on the table are the views that youth live a double standard life, a saved youth will not use slangs and there should be discipline for youth who use unacceptable dancing steps and slangs.

Discussion of Findings

Major findings from this study reveal that young people in campus-based neighbourhood churches have subcultures that describe what goes on around their localities. While the cultures indicated in Table 2 are predominant among young people, the most predominant ones are appearance inclined. Dreadlock is the most predominant with the highest mean of 1.25. This is an indication that some youth wear dreadlocks, and some of these youth are found in the church. Ndu et al. (2017, p. 35) note that dreadlock is a style done by choice among adults. This is not only true for adults but also true for youth. The majority of youth who wear dreadlocks do so by choice and not because their hairs were naturally dreadlocked as the *dada* of Yoruba parlance. One-on-one interactions with some adults in the church revealed that people who wear dreadlocks are easily adjudged as touts. Touts, referred to by the Yoruba people as *omo garage*, were believed to have a “credibility that is depended on their appearance, especially hairstyles...” and “their rugged appearance instills fear in people, distinguishing them as a subgroup

considered to be outlaws and outcasts in the popular imagination” (Agwuele, 2016, p. 84-85). This is a view that some church leaders even extended to youth who are in the church, not minding whether they involve in active services or not. This view, no wonder, rub on their perception that young people engage in a double standard lifestyle since their lifestyle appears not to correspond with the salvation they profess.

The use of slang among young people, which ranked least with a mean value of 0.78 attracts the attention of the church leaders. The use of slang aligns with the view of Mueller who lists slang as part of the cultures of young people that need attention (Mueller, 2006, p. 118). Church leaders affirmed this by desiring to even discipline young people whose languages are over-clouded with slangs, as revealed in Table 3. It will not be out of place for the leaders of the Baptist Church to note that the use of slang is evident among young people because of their interest to play on words and to freely express themselves in a way that they will ensure they understand themselves (Adedun, 2008, p. 5). Considering that the respondents are leaders of campus-based neighbourhood Baptist churches, the use of slang will be clearly evident among the youth of such churches. This is in agreement with Dozie and Madu (2012) who believe that “slang usage is very widespread and fashionable amongst students in higher institutions in Nigeria” (p. 100-101).

Summary of Findings

Summarily, this study reveals that:

1. Church leaders identified the most predominant youth culture in campus-based neighbourhood Baptist churches as dreadlocks, wearing blazers without tucking in the shirt, and wearing socks with slippers in public.
2. Church leader's perceptions of youth culture are negative. This is demonstrated by the view that young people live a double standard life when under the influence of youth culture.
3. Church leaders also believe that young people that are saved will not use slang and that there should be discipline for youth who use unacceptable dancing steps and slang.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research reveals that many church leaders were able to identify the basic predominant youth culture around them, indicating they have a basic understanding of youth and their culture. Despite this understanding, there is still perceived tension between the church leaders and youth. This could be as a result of a lack of proper understanding of how to handle the youth based on the understanding of their culture.

It is therefore recommended that:

1. Church leaders should make deliberate efforts to understand the culture of youth that is peculiar to their environment by being observant, having one-on-one communication with youth, and asking questions from them. They should also take out time to occasionally watch what youth around them view or listen to, which contributes largely to the shaping of youth culture as this will further help their understanding of youth culture and how to reach out to them.
2. The church should organize seminars and workshops on youth culture for the leaders who relate directly and indirectly with young people in order to better equip them for ministry to these young people.
3. Youth discipleship should be more deliberate in order to help them to better understand the concept of salvation.

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